

DENTAL CARE IN CORONAVIRUS INFECTIONS

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Annotation:. Dental and hospital staff are at high risk of respiratory diseases that are regularly transmitted by airborne droplets. Patients may not know if they are infected, and of course, in recent days of high LHT delays due to coronavirus, Logistica reported that the American Dental Association (ADA) has developed several recommendations aimed at isolating the flow of patients to prevent LHT knee infection before covid-19 infection. We know that the dental department of a medical institution is aimed at providing assessment services, as well as taking the necessary measures.

Keywords: coronavirus infection, patient line isolation, prevention, dental care,

Introduction: Dental Emergencies During the covid-19 pandemic, the American Dental Association (ADA) has developed several guidelines to help patients understand what a dental emergency is and what a dental emergency is. The dentist must close the office for all common procedures, such as x-rays and exams, non-infectious tooth extractions, restorative dentistry, and painless treatment of cavities. According to the ADA, emergencies include: * Painful swelling of the mouth * Oral bleeding that won't stop * Toothache or jaw pain * Gum infection, including inflammation or pain * Bandages or stitches * Bleeding from the mouth, ... * If a person has undergone medical oncology treatment, which is assisted remotely by a radiotherapy specialist or a dentist, this will help classify the patient and avoid "unnecessary" visits. During the examination, the gynecologist can measure the patient's body temperature and after the examination can determine whether the patient is in self-isolation, has contact with a patient infected with covid-19, or has

symptoms of the virus. However, despite a thorough examination, the patient can become infected and spread the virus. The risk of infection for a doctor when treating patients with coronavirus infection is 99.99%. Working at a distance of 30-50 cm and using a drill to mix water and air, a uniform spray of aerosols (including the patient's saliva) is formed under pressure, and the drug is easily exhaled with the first breath of the doctor. The same thing happens if the ultrasonic head is used for professional hygiene (a micro mixture of saliva and water is dangerous). The highest level of air pollution from a nebulizer occurs when working with hygiene products such as air flow and when using the technology of cleaning hard dental tissues with proper unprotected sand. During the Covid-19 pandemic, emergency dental care can be provided subject to precautions and rules. These precautions apply to protective masks of the ffp3 layer. Such masks can be used in dry room conditions. When humidified, "breathing" stops. The electrostatic membrane does not work with wet masks, it captures the virus not mechanically, but because it loses its charge when immersed. Therefore, it is necessary to choose masks with exhalation valves - they can work for more than 8 hours (regular masks - about 2 hours). Thus, the use of protective glasses, face shields, FFP3 and Cofeldam masks reduces the risk of infection for dentists. In addition, when contacting a dentist without an aerosol suspension (working with impressions, braces, consultations, etc.). C.) A regular surgical mask is sufficient to protect against infection. The virus itself does not fly out of the air, but is carried by liquid droplets that are formed only if the patient coughs or sneezes without the use of ultrasound or drills (the mask traps such large droplets). During the Covid-19 pandemic, the following dental rules must be followed: do not use turbine heads with a strong air flow, ultrasonic cleaning and sandblasting equipment, and airtight clothing. Or wear a gas mask with ffp3 protection when using them. - During preparation, do not allow air to enter the edges, leaving only water (the ratio can be 1: 1 along the edges of all devices and in all corners). In this case, the particles will be distributed to some

extent. - Use a cofferdam for working with teeth with a drill, which previously eliminated gum leaks and treated the selected tooth or group of teeth with antiseptics. - Be sure to rinse the patient's mouth with disinfectants; - When preparing, use a vacuum cleaner with maximum suction power. - All patients at risk are recommended to use dental preparations for the installation of dental crowns, regular caries treatment, and the removal of dental plaque with ultrasound (these manipulations can only provide emergency dental treatment for 1 month). Remember: the patient may not know that he is already infected, and given the high contagiousness of the coronavirus in the last days of the incubation period, he may infect the dentist! Pathological forms for which emergency care is provided in dental clinics:

- acute (subacute, chronic exacerbation) odontogenic osteomyelitis of the jaw, periostitis;
- fractures of the bones of the facial skull;
- lymphadenitis;
- abscesses and phlegmon in the maxillofacial region;
- exacerbation of chronic maxillary sinusitis;
- * sialadenitis;
- sialolithiasis;
- * furuncle of the face and neck; * retained teeth (dystopia);
- injuries to the lips and soft tissues; • bleeding;
- acute (chronic exacerbation) periodontitis;
- acute (chronic exacerbation) pulpitis;
- acute (chronic exacerbation) periodontitis;
- * dislocation of the mandible; emergency and immediate dental care

Dentists will close their offices for all routine procedures, including x-rays and examinations, tooth extractions without exacerbation of odontogenic infections, restorative dentistry, and treatment of painless cavities. According to the ADA classification, emergency conditions can be considered: • painful swelling in the

mouth;• bleeding in the mouth that does not stop;• pain in the teeth or jaw;• gum infections, including swelling and pain;• bandages and sutures;• wounds or knocked out teeth;* biopsies of abnormal tissue;* correction of dentures if a person has undergone radiation or cancer treatment;* traumatic stomatitis from bracket systems. Experts claim that limiting personal contact is the best way to prevent the spread of COVID–19. Telemedicine comes to the aid of dentists, helping in triage of patients and avoiding “unnecessary” visits. During the visit, the gynecologist can measure the patient’s temperature and clarify whether the person is in self-isolation mode after travel or contact with a COVID-19 patient, regardless of whether he has symptoms characteristic of the virus. However, despite careful screening, there is a possibility that the patient can become infected and spread the virus. The risk of infection for doctors in the treatment of coronavirus patients is 99.99%. Working at a distance of 30-50 cm and using a water-air mixing drill, a finely dispersed aerosol stream (including from the patient's saliva) is created under pressure, penetrating a normal mask with the doctor's first inhalation, like a drug during inhalation. The same happens if an ultrasonic tip is used for professional hygiene (micro-mixtures of water and saliva are dangerous). The maximum level of contamination with water-air spray occurs when using sanitary devices such as air flows, as well as techniques for sandblasting dental hard tissues without appropriate protection. During the COVID-19 pandemic, emergency dental care can be provided, taking into account precautions and following the rules. These precautions are protective masks of the FFP3 class. Such masks can be used in working conditions in a dry environment. When moistened, they stop "breathing". Electrostatic membranes do not work in wet masks, which do not mechanically hold the virus, but due to the charge that is lost when moistened. That's why you need to choose masks with an exhalation valve – they can work from 8 hours or more (normal masks – about 2 hours). Therefore, the use of protective glasses, face shields, FFP3 masks and the use of cofferdams reduces the risk of infection for

dentists. At the same time, when working as a dentist without aerosol suspensions (it is understood that we take impressions, handle braces, consultations, etc.), a conventional surgical mask is enough to protect against infection. The virus does not fly through the air by itself, but travels on droplets that are formed only when the patient coughs or sneezes, without the use of ultrasound or drills (the mask will slow down such large droplets). During the COVID-19 pandemic, the following dental rules should be observed – Do not use turbine tips with strong airflow, ultrasonic, air-abrasive hygiene and sandblasting equipment. Or wear a respirator with FFP3 protection when working with them. - Turn off the air in the tip during preparation, leaving only water (this can be all installations and all corner tips 1:1). In this case, particles will spread to a lesser extent. - Use a cofferdam for work with teeth using a drill that has previously eliminated all gingival leakage and treated selected teeth or groups of teeth with an antiseptic. - Rinsing the patient's oral cavity with a disinfectant is mandatory. - When preparing, use a vacuum cleaner with the greatest suction power. - All patients at risk should undergo dental preparation for a crown, regular treatment of caries, removal of dental deposits with ultrasound (these operations can be performed in a month). Only emergency dental care can be provided. Remember: the patient may not know that he is already infected, and given the high contagiousness of the coronavirus in the last days of the incubation period, he may infect the dentist! Pathological forms for which emergency care is provided in dental clinics:

- acute (subacute, chronic exacerbation) odontogenic osteomyelitis of the jaw, periostitis;
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- * exacerbation of chronic maxillary sinusitis;
- sialadenitis;• sialolithiasis;

- furuncle of the face and neck;
- tooth retention (dystopia);
- damage to the lips and soft tissues;
- bleeding; • acute (chronic exacerbation) periodontitis;
- acute (chronic exacerbation) pulpitis;
- acute (chronic exacerbation) periodontitis;
- * dislocation of the mandible;

To conclude: Precautions that should be implemented by health professionals caring for patients with COVID-19 include the proper use of personal protective equipment (training on how to correctly select, put on, take off and dispose of them). The current stock of personal protective equipment in the country may be limited, so it must be used rationally and appropriately. If personal protective equipment is not used for its intended purpose, we risk being in a situation where we are unable to protect our personnel and the population being served. Standard precautions should be applied at all times in all health care facilities.

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